

INTEGRATION OF READING AND WRITING IN ENGLISH TEACHING (ADAPTATION)

Nazaralieva Matlyubakhon Anarjanovna

Fergana Polytechnic Institute

Teacher of the “Uzbek and Language Teaching” department

e-mail: m.nazaraliyeva@ferpi.uz

ANNOTATION

This article discusses strategies that are helpful in developing reading and writing skills. The need to take into account the age characteristics of students in the development of reading and writing skills is explained on the basis of important evidence. Rather, the activities' integration and this is a crucial word reinforces these languages' inherent interconnectedness. What distinguishes integration is a common objective that forms the basis of all actions. All activities listening, speaking, reading, writing, or any combination of these help an integrated classroom effectively accomplishes its objectives.

Key words and phrases: Young Learners, Adult Learners, Critical Process, Include, Identify, Language Learning, Vocabulary Check, Comprehension, Critical Approach to Reading Comprehension, Demand Response giving

INTRODUCTION

Obviously, it usually requires a separation of language components, and this is divided into separate reading, writing, literature and communication courses. Incorporating these four areas into every course is the first step toward integration, and how listening, speaking, and reading activities are done in the classroom determines their effectiveness. It is not enough to provide separate activities for diversity; The only thing that these activities have in common is that they all take place in the same room. Instead, the integration of activities (and integration is the key word here) reinforces the natural interdependence of these languages. A unifying goal that underlies all activities is what sets integration apart. In an integrated classroom, all activities listening, speaking, reading, writing, or any combination of these help to achieve the goal effectively. One way to organize the curriculum like the goals designed for the integrated approach is a thematically based course.

THEORY AND RESEARCH

The above definition examines from a theoretical and research point of view what is meant by an integrated approach to the activities of listening, speaking, reading and writing in the classroom. Now, on the topic of “What is Integration?” the question “Why is it necessary to combine itself?” changes to the question.

In general, the discussion for the integration approach in the English classroom focuses on how children learn language. Much of the research on language development involves language skills in young children. In *Psycholinguistics: A Cognitive View of Language*, Helen and Charles Cairns describe the stages of linguistic development from babbling, one word, two They explain the types of sentences, now developing grammar, from almost adult grammar to full proficiency. They further generalize language development into the general domain of Piagetian cognitive development. Cairns, however, does not base his argument on a theory of oral language learning.

Bradford Arthur *Teaching English to English Speakers* explains the teacher-oriented principles of “Natural Language Learning” in his book ; By this he also means “natural language learning” and “natural” rather than artificial or mechanical methods of natural language learning. Arthur says that language learning is natural for all children, so teaching methods should foster each student's natural language learning tendency. It describes the process of learning several aspects of a language step by step, as part of a developmental process. In the case of natural language learning, the child covers many areas of the language at the same time. For this reason, no one should teach in isolation.[1]

Bradford Arthur's views are similar to Constance Weaver's parallels of speaking and reading in the natural processes of learning. In *Psycholinguistics and the Reading Process: From Process to Practice*, Weaver argues that a process cannot be directly “taught”; Instead, children need to learn how the language system works. Arthur and Weaver argue that teachers must have the ability to learn language in a natural language environment. Weaver also parallels the theme of deeply structured written language. For example, he cites the example of “Mommy sock” in which “Mommy sock” has multiple meanings based on the spoken surface structure. This example from spoken language forces children to focus on the meanings of young readers while misinterpreting reading for the first time. A final parallel that Weaver draws involves errors in verbal generalization and reading for meaning. Weaver

concludes his remarks with the simple statement that people “learn by trying to hear and use language themselves in natural and meaningful contexts.”

The work of Mark Aulls and Marilyn Wilson outlines the current state of literacy integration. In his “Recent Research Paper on Reading and Writing Connections,” Wilson makes a strong case for active coupling between the two processes. The conclusion of this study is that when reading and writing are combined in the classroom, they complement each other. Aulls explains his findings in Realizing Reading Comprehension and Writing based on informal classroom observations. He raved about how the exercises in the combination of reading and writing helped his students, both passive and excellent readers.[2]

THE PROCESS

Although articles or books on integration explore the interrelated processes in the elementary school, James Moffitt articulates this theory more broadly in his 13th grade book for teachers. Moffett discusses pitfalls and gaps in classroom management skills and provides a theoretically integrated curriculum through the thirteenth grade. Based on student-centered classroom design, Moffett focuses on engaging in a variety of listening, speaking, reading, and writing exercises. It describes extensive training, explains how to use it in the classroom, and gives examples. In other words, he skillfully tackles the idea of the curriculum, but he ignores the learning skills that integrate these ideas in the course.

OBJECTIVES AND DUTIES

In the Teacher's Guide, Stephen and Susan Judy recommend instructional essentials to help plan voice courses. The following list of initial goals and objectives should help design courses that are aligned in terms of structure, materials, and learner engagement.

Also, all combined activities ensure the development of the student's language learning.

Second, courses and topics should be based on a variety of issues, such as family, men and women, aging, human dignity, cities, and heroism. Additionally, a unique feature of the thematic framework is that it ensures that true alignment occurs. A variety of listening, speaking, reading and writing exercises without a common goal will lead nowhere. Also, the variety of choices and exercises increases the student's knowledge.

Third, the variety of textbooks and materials is an important part of English language teaching. Diversity should not be a mistake because it is a means to achieve the goal of the lesson. It is important to provide students with more resources and experiences in showing the full potential of the subject. In addition, many materials better familiarize the reader with the topic. As a result, student identification increases personal relevance that increases interest and engages them in the lesson.

Fourth, writing theory as a structural process should be developed as an important part of the course. Emphasis should be placed on planning, proofreading, revision, editing, and publishing. Traditionally, writing has been isolated as an extracurricular activity. Also, writing skills interact with other language skills. For example, a whole class or small group can use listening and speaking to help develop writing. In the draft, students work alone, but they are especially enthusiastic when they are working on the same task as a group. The stages of review, editing, and publication directly integrate language processes. During the final stages of writing, they read their own and their friends' papers, explain them through oral and written responses, and prepare their writing for their peers as potential reading material. Therefore, writing skills should not be overlooked.[3]

Finally, free or instructor-sponsored private reading, writing, and exchange should be incorporated into the course design. With study sessions devoted to individually selected study materials and open time for journaling, students can explore topics and subtopics that interest them. We hope that due attention to the periods of reading and writing will create the most important harmonious equality in the minds of students. Students can write a song, lyric poem, short story, joke, caricature, or personal experience that fits the theme of the topic or lesson. Thus, students verbally express interest in themselves and the lesson, other students listen and share experiences. The intention of reading, writing and sharing in terms of somewhat limited freedom is quite simple: that is, to ensure that individual students 'dominate' rather than whole-class assignments with a flow of ideas in all interactive language processes.

With the principles of a comprehensive approach defined as understanding, theory, research and principles, the stage is set to depict a course that combines listening, speaking, reading and writing with daily activities. The course revolves around the theme of the central character. The development of the character comes mainly from the point of view of the chronological sequence of the literature.

Nevertheless, the unifying quality of the thematic base protects this direction from deviating into irrelevant parts. In addition, within the overall content of the lesson, the units can be reorganized with special emphasis on tracing different aspects of the character's development. In other words, the order of the units presented does not matter; if the chosen order corresponds to the development tendency of the character, the pursuit of the goal will be stable. A brief description of all selected classroom activities is provided below.

After students finish reading, they participate in a “written interview.” In this second event, readers write responses that range from personal reactions to more analytical insights into the presentation style, the characters, the “Everyman” heroism, the antiquity, and the relevance of the play to the modern world. The informality of the “written discussion” class notes emphasize thoughtful reaction rather than vociferous output. Armed with their personal notes, students briefly discuss the short but powerful answers.[4]

Each student should be prepared for activity number three after participating and through written and oral discussion of the two activities, along with the teacher's responses. This activity involves breaking the group into small groups to practice an 'everyman' game that can be performed by their peers in the school auditorium. Each group decides on a voice recorder to prepare the current version of “Everyman” for their thoughts and decisions. When the groups are finished, have each representative quickly present the group's ideas to the whole class.

The fourth activity depends on the students deciding what to do next. They vote for one of three options:

(1) each group produces and manages its own class for other classes or for other classes;

(2) a class classically produces and controls one of the subgroups and executes for other classes ;

(3) the two things listed above should not carry over to the next. If students are interested enough, they will choose the first or second option. Once it is known which version and which audience have been identified, the task is now to put them into practice.

Chapter “An Ancient Mariner's Rime”.

The overall purpose of The Ancient Mariner is to engage students in an experience that allows them to determine whether the Mariner is a hero in their eyes

and in Coleridge's eyes. The specific goals of the first two activities are to engage students more in literature, to engage students actively and creatively in forecasting, to encourage them to identify and adhere to specific elements and themes, and to encourage students to engage in what some students call “boring stuff.” bringing something to life. This unit provides responsive solutions that reflect literature, reinforces that literature has some subject matter, but is always influenced by the author's creativity, and encourages students to see themselves as writers and readers. [5]

The first activity involves students silently reading the first five chapters of *The Ancient Mariner's Rime*. For this activity to be successful, students must stop reading after completing the fifth chapter. They participate in an informal discussion in which their attitude toward the Mariner and his actions must be consistent with the narrator's plot. [6]

In the second activity, students participate in creating their own version of how the Mariner's story ended. Students don't have to keep the rhythm and rhyme, but they do have to keep the ideas consistent with the Mariner's point of view. If students create open-ended questions about the Mariner's repentance, finality, and heroic qualities, along with questions about the role of spirits and the fate of the crew, they remove obstacles to the writing process. Students mark their conclusions as “good” or “not good” and the teacher reads them to the whole class.

The third activity closes the unit. Students read passages of poetry and then respond to what they have written, the object being to reflect on the relationship between themselves and Coleridge's connections. The discussion concludes by exploring the similarities and differences in each ending and discussing how and why the Mariner's life is portrayed differently.

The main purpose of the comic book is to convey emotional, reflective and creative feelings to the comic book superhero. In the first session, students read a book of their choice. After about thirty minutes, students stop reading the textbook to think through the book with their characters as literature. Later, the content and composition of this type will be discussed in class. [7]

For example, content may deal with fantasy, action, illustration, anti-hero, anti-villain, anti-villain, and right and wrong behavior. Descriptions of structure may include short sentences, simple language, rapid transitions, and a general formula of

general heroism, conflict, structure, closure, and clarity. After a general discussion, students should think about a superhero they have created and want to write about.

Second, students try to develop a unique superhero, write a comic book, and work collaboratively and effectively in a small group. There are five groups, and the work is divided according to the following positions: Editor-in-chief, Script consultant, Author, illustrator, cover artist. Although each group member develops the comic book as a whole, each person responds at a separate stage.

After the groups have finished their comics, the whole class comes back together to express their reactions to the creation of literature and participate in the creations of other peer writers.

CONCLUSION

Here are the main section activities that work; that is, students treat them well. Students are attracted to the variety of daily activities; continuous research of the subject of the lesson maintains high interest and enthusiasm; attention to the interrelationship of listening, speaking, reading, and writing is devoted entirely to language. The character units in this course are only examples of an integrated approach to English language teaching. In fact, the integrated approach is a methodology that assimilates the results of recent research on the interdependence of language learning. The success of the lesson depends on the teacher's goal of the lessons and the integration of activities aimed at long-term language development.

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